

Review Article

Current approaches in buccal drug delivery system

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ABSTRACT

Buccal delivery involves the administration of the desired drug through the buccal mucosal membrane lining of the oral cavity. The objective of this article is to review buccal drug delivery by discussing the structure and environment of the oral mucosa and highlighting the mechanisms of drug permeation and methodology in evaluating buccal formulations. This review also highlights a brief description of advantages, limitations of buccal drug delivery and theories involved in mucoadhesion along with method of preparation mucoadhesive system, mucoadhesive polymer, and classification of buccal system.

Keywords: Buccal drug delivery, Mucoadhesion, Polymers for buccal drug delivery

Introduction

The pharmaceutical industry has made itself of significant importance making it a major contribution in the healthcare industry. The improvement and developments made by pharmaceutical industry have significantly donated in relationships of treatment of disease, thereby improving the quality of life.² Among the delivery routes, oral routes is most preferred route by medical practitioner and manufacturer due to highest acceptability of patients, ease of ingestion, pain avoidance and versatility.¹

The cost involved both in terms of money and time in the development of a particular new chemical entity has made it obligatory for pharmaceutical firms to reconsider delivery approaches to improve the efficacy of drugs that have already been approved. Because of low cost, ease of administration and high level of patient compliance the oral route is perhaps the most preferred to the patient and clinician alike. However administration of drugs has short term

limitations like first pass metabolism, which leads to a lack significant correlation between Membrane Permeability, Absorption, Bioavailability and Drug degradation within the gastro intestinal (GI) tract that forbid oral administration of certain classes of drugs eg. proteins and peptides. Other absorptive mucosae, are considered as prospective site for drug administration. Transmucosal routes (mucosal lining of nasal, rectal, vaginal, ocular and oral cavity) offers some distinct advantages such as possible bypass of the first pass effect, avoidance of pre systemic elimination within the GIT and better enzymatic flora for drug absorption.³⁻⁵

Within the oral mucosal cavity, delivery of drugs can be categorised into three classes:

- Buccal delivery
- Sublingual delivery
- Local delivery

- **Buccal delivery:** Buccal delivery is drug administration over the mucosal membranes lining the cheeks (buccal mucosa)
- **Sublingual delivery:** Sublingual delivery is systemic delivery of drugs through the mucosal membranes lining the surface of the mouth
- **Local delivery:** Local delivery is drug delivery among the oral cavity.

Advantages of buccal drug delivery system

- Buccal drug delivery system has following advantages over conventional drug delivery systems.
- Persists the residence time of the dosage form at the absorption site, hence rises the bioavailability.
- Outstanding availability, rapid onset of action possible.
- Fast absorption because of huge blood supply and good perfusion rates.
- An alternative to oral route, whereby the drug is secure from degradation in the acidic environment of the GIT.
- Preferable patient acquiescence.
- Likewise, rapid cellular recuperating and healing of the local site.
- In this, there is reduced dosing frequency.
- It required shorter treatment period.
- Developed safety margin of high strength drugs due to better control of plasma levels.
- Extreme utilization of drug facilitating reduction in total amount of drug administered.⁷⁻⁹

Limitations of buccal drug delivery system

- By this route the drugs, which irritate the oral mucosa, have a bitter or unpleasant taste, odour cannot be administered.
- Only drugs, which are absorbed by passive diffusion, can be administered by this route.
- By this route, drugs which are unstable at buccal pH, cannot be administered
- Only drugs with lesser dose requirements can be administered.
- Drugs may be swallowed along with the saliva and fail the benefits of buccal route.
- Eating and drinking may become restricted.
- It may get displaced.
- Over hydration may lead to the formation of slippery surface and structural integrity of the

formulation may get disrupted by the swelling and hydration of the bio-adhesive polymers.⁷⁻⁹

Ideal characteristics^{10,11}:

- Polymer and its degradation products should be non-poisonous, non-irritant and free from leachable impurities.
- Should have good spreadability, wetting, swelling and solubility and biodegradability properties.
- pH should be biocompatible and should hold good viscoelastic properties.
- Should adhere quickly to buccal mucosa and should have sufficient mechanical strength.
- It must possess peel, tensile and shear strengths at the bio-adhesive range.
- Polymer must be simply available and inexpensive.
- In dry and liquid state it should possess bio-adhesion properties.
- It should exhibit local enzyme inhibition and penetration enhancement properties.
- It should show suitable shelf life.
- The molecular weight should be optimum.
- It should have adhesively active groups.
- It should have required spatial conformation. It should be adequately cross-linked but not to the degree of suppression of bond forming groups.
- It should not support in development of secondary infections such as dental caries.

Overview of oral mucosa

Figure 1: Oral mucosa.

The anatomical and physiological properties of oral mucosa had been extensively reviewed by several authors.¹³⁻¹⁵ The oral cavity comprises the lips, cheek, tongue, hard palate, soft palate and floor of the mouth. The lining of the oral cavity is referred to as the oral mucosa, and includes the buccal, sublingual, gingival, palatal and labial mucosa. The buccal, sublingual and the mucosal tissues at the ventral surface of the tongue accounts for about 60% of the oral mucosal surface area. The top quarter to one-third of the oral mucosa is made up of closely compacted epithelial cells. The primary function of the oral epithelium is to protect the underlying tissue against potential harmful agents in the oral environment and from fluid loss.¹⁶ Beneath the epithelium are the basement membrane, lamina propria and submucosa. The oral mucosa also contains many sensory receptors including the taste receptors of the tongue.

Three types of oral mucosa can be found in the oral cavity; the lining mucosa is found in the outer oral vestibule (the buccal mucosa) and the sublingual region (floor of the mouth). The specialised mucosa is found on the dorsal surface of tongue, while the masticatory mucosa is found on the hard palate (the upper surface of the mouth) and the gingiva (gums).¹⁷ The lining mucosa comprises approximately 60%, the masticatory mucosa approximately 25%, and the specialized mucosa approximately 15% of the total surface area of the oral mucosal lining in an adult human. The masticatory mucosa is located in the regions particularly susceptible to the stress and strains resulting from masticatory activity. The superficial cells of the masticatory mucosa are keratinized, and a thick lamina propria tightly binds the mucosa to underlying periosteum. Lining mucosa on the other hand is not nearly as subject to masticatory loads and consequently, has a

non-keratinized epithelium, which sits on a thin and elastic lamina propria and a submucosa. The mucosa of the dorsum of the tongue is specialized gustatory mucosae, which has a well papillated surface; which are both keratinized and some non-keratinized.¹⁸

Bioadhesion¹⁹⁻²²

‘Bioadhesive’ is defined as a substance that is capable of interacting with biological material and being retained on them or holding them together for persistent period of time.

Bioadhesive are classified into three categories.

- Bioadhesion among biological layers without involvement of artificial materials. e.g. Cell diffusion and cell aggregation
- Bioadhesion can be showed by cell adhesion into culture dishes or adhesion to a variety of substances including metals, woods and other synthetic materials.
- Adhesion of artificial substances to biological substrate such as adhesion of polymer to soft tissue or skin.

Mechanism of bioadhesion^{19,22-25}

For bio-adhesion to occur, three steps take place:

- A close contact among a bioadhesive and a membrane either from a good wetting of the bioadhesive and a membrane or from the swelling of bioadhesive.
- Penetration of the bio-adhesive into the tissue takes place.
- Inter penetration of the chains of the bioadhesive with mucous takes place. Low chemical bonds can then settle.

The bonding between the mucus and the biological substance occurs mainly through both physical and chemical interactions results from expansion of the adhesive material and chemical bonds due to electrostatic interaction, hydrophobic interactions, hydrogen bonding and dispersion forces.

Figure 2: Inter penetration of bioadhesive and mucus polymer chain.

Factors affecting bioadhesion²

Structural and physicochemical properties of a potential bioadhesion material influence bioadhesion.

A. Polymer related factors

a. Molecular weight:

- The bioadhesive force rises with molecular weight of polymer upto 10,000 and beyond this level there is no much effect.
- To allow chain interpenetration, the polymer molecule must have an adequate length.

b. Concentration of active polymers:

- There is an ideal concentration of polymer resultant to the best bioadhesion.
- In extremely concentrated systems, the adhesive strength drops considerably.
- In concentrated solutions, the coiled molecules become solvent poor and the chains presented for interpenetration are not abundant.

c. Flexibility of polymer chain:

- Flexibility is necessary part for interpenetration and enlargement.
- When water soluble polymers become cross linked, the mobility of individual polymer chain declines.
- As the cross linking density increases, the effective length of the chain which can penetrate into the mucus layer drops further and mucoadhesive strength is reduced.

d. Spatial conformation:

- Beside molecular weight or chain length, spatial conformation of a molecule is also important.
- Despite a high molecular weight of 19,500,000 for dextrans, they have same adhesive strength

to that of polyethylene glycol with a molecular weight of 200,000.

- The helical conformation of dextran may shield many adhesively active groups, primarily responsible for adhesion, different PEG polymers which have a linear conformation.

B. Environment related factors:

a. pH:

The pH influences the charge on the surface of both mucus and the polymers. Mucus will have a different charge density depending on pH. Because of change in dissociation of functional groups on the Carbohydrate moiety and amino acids of the polypeptide backbone.

b. Strength:

To place a solid bioadhesive system, it is necessary to apply a defined strength.

c. Initial contact time:

As soon as the mucoadhesive strength increases, the initial contact time is also increases.

d. Selection of the model substrate surface:

The viability of biological substrate should be confirmed by examining properties such as permeability, Electrophysiology of histology.

e. Swelling:

Swelling depends on both polymers concentration and on presence of water. When swelling is too great a decrease in bioadhesion occurs.

Theories of bioadhesion or mucoadhesion^{10, 11,20, 21, 23,24.}

Some theories have been suggested to explain the fundamental mechanism of adhesion.

a. Wetting theory:

Wetting theory is predominantly applicable to liquid bioadhesive systems and analyses adhesive and contact behaviour in terms of a liquid or a paste to spread over a biological system. The work of adhesion [expressed in terms of surface and interfacial tension (γ)] being defined as energy per cm^2 released when an interface is formed.

According to Dupres equation, work of adhesion is given by

$$W_A = \gamma_A + \gamma_B - \gamma_{AB}$$

Where, A and B refers to the biological membrane and the bioadhesive formulation respectively.

The work of cohesion is given by

$$W_c = 2\gamma_A \text{ or } \gamma_B$$

For a bioadhesive material B spreading on a biological substrate, the spreading coefficient is given by:

$$S_{B/A} = \gamma_A - (\gamma_B + \gamma_{AB})$$

$S_{B/A}$ should be positive for a bioadhesive material to adhere to a biological membrane. For a bioadhesive liquid B adhering to a biological membrane A, the contact angle is given by:

$$\cos \gamma = (\gamma_A - \gamma_{AB} / \gamma_B).$$

Figure 3: Contact angle.

b. Diffusion theory:

According to this theory, the polymer chains and the mucus mix to a sufficient depth to create a semi-permanent adhesive bond. The exact depth to which the polymer chains penetrate the mucus depends on the diffusion coefficient and the time of contact. This diffusion coefficient, in turn, depends on the value of molecular weight among cross links and drops considerably as the cross linking density decreases.

Figure 4: Secondary interaction between mucoadhesive device and mucus.

c. Electronic theory:

According to this theory, electronic relocation occurs upon contact of an adhesive polymer and the mucus glycoprotein network because of differences in their electronic structure. This result in the formulation of an electronic double layer at the interface adhesion occurs due to attractive forces across the double layer.

d. Fracture theory:

According to Fracture theory of adhesion is related to separation of two surfaces after adhesion. The fracture strength is equivalent to adhesive strength as given by,

$$G = (E\epsilon / L)^{1/2}$$

Where: E= Young's module of elasticity

ϵ = Fracture energy

L= Critical crack length when two surfaces are separated.

Figure 5: Fractures occurring for mucoadhesion.

e. Adsorption theory:

According to this theory, after an initial contact between two surfaces, the materials adhere because of surface forces acting between the atoms in the two surfaces. Two types of chemical bonds such as primary covalent (permanent) and secondary chemical bonds (including electrostatic forces, Vander-waal's forces and hydrogen and hydrophobic bonds) are involved in the adsorption process.

Basic components of buccal drug delivery system^{19,26}

The basic components of buccal drug delivery system are Drug substance

- a. Bio adhesive polymers

- b. Backing membrane
- c. Permeation enhancers

Figure 6: The process of consolidation.

a. Drug substance:

Before formulating mucoadhesive drug delivery systems, one has to decide whether the intended, action is for rapid release/prolonged release and for local/systemic effect. The selection of suitable drug for the design of buccoadhesive drug delivery systems should be based on pharmacokinetic properties.

The drug should have following characteristics:²⁷

- The conventional single dose of the drug should be small.
- The drugs having biological half-life between 2-8 hrs are good candidates for controlled drug delivery.
- Tmax of the drug shows wider-fluctuations or higher values when given orally.
- Through oral route drug may exhibit first pass effect or pre-systemic drug elimination.

b. Bioadhesive polymer:

The first step in the development of buccoadhesive dosage forms is the selection and Characterization of appropriate bio adhesive polymers in the formulation. Bio adhesive polymers play a major role in buccoadhesive drug delivery systems of drugs. Polymers are also used in matrix devices in which the drug is embedded in

the polymer matrix, which control the duration of release of drugs.²⁸ Bioadhesive polymers are from the most diverse class and they have considerable benefits upon patient health care and treatment.²⁹ The drug is released into the mucous membrane by means of rate controlling layer or core layer. Bio adhesive polymers which adhere to the mucin/epithelial surface are effective and lead to significant improvement in the oral drug delivery.³⁰

An ideal polymer for buccoadhesive drug delivery systems should have following characteristics.^{31,32}

- It should be inert and compatible with the environment
- The polymer and its degradation products should be non-toxic absorbable from the mucous layer.
- It should adhere quickly to moist tissue surface and should possess some site specificity.
- The polymer must not decompose on storage or during the shelf life of the dosage form.
- The polymer should be easily available in the market and economical.
- It should allow easy incorporation of drug in to the formulation.

Criteria followed in polymer selection

- It should form a strong non covalent bond with the mucine/epithelial surface
- It must have high molecular weight and narrow distribution.
- It should be compatible with the biological membrane.

The commonly used as bio adhesive polymers in pharmaceutical applications are in Table 1.

c. Backing membrane:

Backing membrane plays a major role in the attachment of bioadhesive devices to the mucous membrane. The materials used as backing membrane should be inert, and impermeable to the drug and penetration enhancer. Such

Table 1: Mucoadhesive Polymers used in the oral cavity.³³

Criteria	Categories	Examples
Source	Semi natural/ Natural	Agarose, chitosan, gelatin, Hyaluronic acid, Various gums (guar gum, xanthan, gellan, carrageenan, pectin and sodium alginate).
	Synthetic	Cellulose derivatives: [CMC, thiolated CMC, NaCMC, HEC, HPC, HPMC,MC.] Poly (acrylic acid)-based polymers: [CP, PC, PAA, polyacrylates, poly (methyl vinyl ether-co-methacrylic acid), poly (2- hydroxy ethyl methacrylate), poly (acrylic acid-co-ethyl hexyl acrylate), poly (methacrylate), poly (isobutyl-cyanoacrylate), copolymer of acrylic acid and PEG]. Others: polyoxyethylene, PVA, PVP, thiolated Polymers.
Aqueous solubility	Water soluble	CP, HEC, HPC, HPMC (cold water), PAA, NaCMC, sodium alginate.
	Water insoluble	Chitosan (soluble in dilute aqueous acids), EC, PC.
Charge	Cationic	Aminodextran, Chitosan, (DEAE)- dextran, TMC
	Anionic	Chitosan-EDTA, CP, CMC, pectin, PAA, PC, sodium alginate, NaCMC, xanthan gum.
	Non-ionic	Hydroxy ethyl starch, HPC, poly(ethylene oxide), PVA,
Potential	Covalent	PVP, scleroglucan
	Hydrogen bond	Cyanoacrylate
Bioadhesive forces	Electrostatic interaction	Acrylates [hydroxylatedmethacrylate,poly(methacrylic acid)], CP, PC, PVA, Chitosan

Table 2: Examples of permeation enhancers with mechanism.¹⁹

Category	Examples	Mechanism
Surfactants and Bile Salts	Surfactants and Bile Salts Sodium dodecyl sulphate Sodium lauryl sulphate Polysorbate 80	Acting on the components at tight junctions Increasing the fluidity of lipid bilayer membrane;
Fatty Acids	Oleic acid, Cod liver oil, Capric acid, Lauric acid	Increasing the fluidity of lipid bilayer membrane.
Polymers and Polymer Derivatives	ChitosanTrimethyl chitosanChitosan-4- thiobutylamide	Increasing the fluidity of lipid bilayer membrane; Increased retention of drug at mucosal surface.
Others	Ethanol, Azone, Octisalate, Padimate, Menthol	Acting on the components at tight junctions; Increasing the fluidity of lipid bilayer membrane

impermeable membrane on buccal bioadhesive patches prevents the drug loss and offers better patient compliance. The commonly used materials in backing membrane include carbopol, magnesium stearate, HPMC, HPC, CMC, polycarbophil etc.³⁴

d. Permeation enhancers:

Substances that facilitate the permeation through buccal mucosa are referred as permeation

enhancers. Selection of enhancer and its efficacy depends on the physicochemical properties of the drug, site of administration, nature of the vehicle and other excipients.

Mechanisms of action of permeation:

- i. Changing mucus rheology:
By reducing the viscosity of the mucus and saliva overcomes this barrier.

- ii. Increasing the fluidity of lipid bilayer membrane:
Disturb the intracellular lipid packing by interaction with either lipid packing by interaction with either lipid or protein components.
- iii. Acting on the components at tight junctions:
By inhibiting the various peptidases and proteases present within buccal mucosa, thereby overcoming the enzymatic barrier.

In addition, changes in membrane fluidity also alter the enzymatic activity indirectly.
- iv. Increasing the thermodynamic activity of drugs:
Some enhancers increase the solubility of drug there by alters the partition coefficient.

Classification of buccal systems³⁵

Recent buccal mucoadhesive formulations prove to be an alternative to the conventional oral medications as they can be readily attached to the buccal cavity retained for a longer period of time and removed at any time. Mucoadhesive drug delivery systems using tablets, films, layered systems, discs, micro particles, ointments, wafers, lozenges and hydrogel systems has been studied by various research groups.

1. Buccal tablets

Bioadhesive tablets may be prepared using different methods such as direct compression or wet granulation technique. For delivery of drug via buccal route, the tablets which are inserted into the buccal pouch may dissolve or erode; therefore, they must be formulated and compressed with sufficient pressure only to give a hard tablet. To enable or to achieve unidirectional release of drug, water impermeable materials, like ethyl cellulose, hydrogenated castor oil, etc. may be used either by compression or by spray coating to coat every face of the tablet except the one that is in contact with the buccal mucosa. Bilayered and multilayered tablets are already formulated using bioadhesive polymers and excipients. If necessary, the drug may be formulated in certain physical states, such as microspheres, prior to direct compression in order to attain some

desired properties e.g. enhanced activity and prolonged drug release.

2. Buccal semisolid dosage forms

These are semisolid dosage forms having the advantage of easy dispersion throughout the oral mucosa over the other type of dosage forms. Bioadhesive formulations have been used to overcome the poor retention of gels on the buccal mucosa. Certain bioadhesive polymers for example, sodium carboxy methylcellulose undergo a phase alteration from a liquid to a semisolid. This alteration improves or enhances the viscosity, resulting in sustained or controlled release of drugs. Buccal bioadhesive semisolid dosage forms consists of finely powdered natural or synthetic polymer dispersed in a polyethylene or in aqueous solution like Arabase.

3. Buccal films

In recent years, numerous bioadhesive dosage forms for delivery of drug via the buccal route have been developed such as films, tablet, patches, discs, gels and ointments. Buccal films are preferable over mucoadhesive discs and tablets in terms of patient comfort and flexibility and they ensure more precise drug dosing and longer residence time compared to gels and ointments and thereby sustaining drug action. Buccal films also reduce pain by protecting wound surface and increasing drug effectiveness.

4. Buccal powders

Buccal bioadhesive powders are a mixture of drug and Bioadhesive polymers. Which are sprayed onto the buccal mucosa, the reduction in diastolic B.P. after the administration of buccal tablet and buccal film of nifedipine.

5. Micro particle

Micro particles have more advantages than tablet. The physical properties of microspheres enable to make them closely contact with a large mucosal surface. They can also be delivered to less accessible sites like GI track and nasal cavity and they causeless local irritation at the

site of adhesion but the success of these microspheres is limited due to their short residence time at site of absorption.

6. Wafer

Wafer is a novel periodontal drug delivery system. This is used for the treatment of microbial infection.

7. Lozenges

Lozenges are used as topically within mouth including antimicrobials, corticosteroids, local anaesthetics, antibiotics and antifungals. In lozenges multiple daily dosing is required because the release of drug in oral cavity is initially high and then rapidly decline to the subtherapeutic levels.

8. Buccal patches

These are flexibles which deliver the drugs straight in to systemic circulation over mucus membrane thus by passing the first pass effect. Buccal patch formulations are placed in the mouth between the upper gingivae (gums) and cheek to treat local and systemic conditions. Interaction with digestive food of gastrointestinal tract is avoided which might be inappropriate for stability of many drugs. This is easy, painless and without discomfort, precise dosage form and facilitates ease of removal without significant related pain. Moreover it shows better constancy, patient compliance; uniform and sustained drug release and above all easy and cheap methods of preparation which can be done with various commonly available biocompatible polymers.

Evaluation parameter of buccal patches³⁶

Weight variation

For evaluation of film weight, three films of every formulation are selected randomly and individual weight of each 1x1cm patch was taken on digital balance. The average weight was calculated.³⁷

a. Film thickness

Thickness of the film is measured by using screw gauge with a least count of 0.01 mm at different places on the film. The thickness of the film was measured at three different places and the average of thickness is measured.³⁷

b. Surface pH

For determination of surface pH three films of each formulation is allowed in contact with 1ml of distilled water. The surface pH was noted by bringing a combined glass electrode or pH paper near the surface of films and allowing equilibrate for 1 min. A mean of three reading is recorded.³⁸

c. Folding endurance

Folding endurance of the film is determined by repeatedly folding one film at the same place till it broke, which was considered satisfactory to reveal good films properties. The number of times of films could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the value of the folding endurance. This test was done on randomly selected three films from each formulation.³⁹

d. Drug content uniformity

This parameter was determined by dissolving film of 1 × 1cm diameter containing drug in 50 ml simulated salivary fluid with occasional shaking. Filtration was carried out to remove insoluble residue, 1 ml of the filtrate was diluted to 10 ml with simulated salivary fluid (pH 6.8). The absorbance was measured at specified nm using an UV spectrophotometer. The experiments were carried out in triplicate for the films of all formulations.^{39,40}

e. In-vitro dissolution studies

Dissolution study was carried out in USP basket type apparatus using the stimulated salivary fluid (pH 6.8) as a dissolution medium at 50 rotations per minute. 10 ml aliquots were withdrawn at one minute time intervals and same amount of fresh dissolution medium was added. The aliquots were assayed for drug content at specified wavelength using UV-spectrophotometer. The cumulative percentage drug release was calculated.⁴¹

f. *Moisture absorption*

The moisture absorption study of films was done at a relative humidity of 75% for a period of three days. The low moisture uptake by all the formulations was observed at 75% relative humidity. The low moisture uptake by all the buccal films can help to retard any hydrolytic degradation, and films will remain stable.⁴²

g. *Swelling studies*

The degree of swelling is determined in phosphate buffer pH 6.8. All batches have good swelling properties which remain hydrated for longer time. All formulations were swelled within 10 min and which delayed the swelling after 2 h i.e. constant weight of the buccal patch is seen. It is highlighted that swelling properties are important when film integrity is evaluated.⁴³

h. *Percent elongation at break*

For the determination of percentage elongation of the film formulations, the distance between the tensile grips of the tensile strength testing machine was measured before and after the fracture of the film and calculated the % elongation of patch by using the following formula Then the percentage elongation of the films was computed with the help of the formula given below.⁴⁴

$$\% \text{ Elongation at break} = \frac{\text{Increase in length}}{\text{Initial length}} \times 100$$

i. *Dispersion test*

A strip equivalent to 5 mg of drug placed in 200 ml of 6.8pH phosphate buffer and was stirred for 3 minutes. The resulting solution was passed through sieve number 22. The film is said to be passed the dispersion test only when no residue is left on the sieve.⁴⁵

j. *In vitro residence/mucoadhesion time*

The in vitro adhesion time of films was evaluated by assessing the time for the patch to detach from goat buccal mucosa in a well stirred beaker filled with 500 ml phosphate buffer pH 6.8 at 37 °C. The mucosal membrane was fixed on the side of the beaker with cyanoacrylate glue. The patch was attached to the membrane by applying light force with finger tip for 60 sec.

The beaker was then magnetically stirred at an approximate rate of 150 rpm to simulate buccal and saliva movement. The time necessary for complete erosion or detachment of the films from the mucosal membrane was taken as an indication of the in vitro adhesion time.^{45,46}

k. *Tensile strength*

Tensile strength of the buccal films was determined by using universal strength testing machine. The sensitivity of the machine is one gram. It consists of 2 load cell grips. The lower one is fixed and upper one is movable as shown in the figure. The test patch of specific size is fixed between these cell grips and force was gradually applied, till the patch breaks. The tensile strength of the patch was taken directly from the dial reading.⁴⁰

l. *Percentage Moisture content*

The buccal patches is weighed accurately and kept in desiccators containing anhydrous calcium chloride. After three days, the patches were taken out and weighed. The moisture content (%) was determined by the formula⁴⁷.

$$\% \text{ Moisture content} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

m. *Effect of temperature and humidity*

Effect of temperature and humidity of optimization formulation was carried out for one month at 40 °C ± 2 °C, 75 % ± 5% RH maintained in environmental stability chamber. The patches were wrapped in aluminium foil and exposed to the said conditions. Samples were evaluated at 0, 7, 14, 21 and 28 days for the parameters as

- i. Appearance
- ii. Surface pH
- iii. Folding endurance
- iv. Drug release (%)^{48,49}

Conclusions

Due to success, advantages and ease of access of drug delivery through oral mucosal tissue the buccal and sublingual routes have favourable opportunities and many formulation approaches; although the current commercially available

formulation are mostly limited to tablets and films.

The buccal mucosa offers several advantages for controlled drug delivery for long period of time and also favourable area for systemic delivery of orally unsatisfactory drugs and attractive alternative for non-offensive delivery of potent peptide and protein drug molecule.

There is renewed interest and active product development activity for following generation of oral mucosal delivery system. Oral mucohesive dosage forms will continue be an exciting research focus for improving drug absorption especially for the new generation.

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